

EVIDENCE OF CARBOXY ESTER MECHANISMS
IN NITRIFICATION FROM THE DYNAMIC
REACTION KINETICS AT NATURAL
CONCENTRATIONS.

Part IV. Nitrite Oxidation in Nitrification Follows
Michaelis-Menten Kinetics at Low Concentrations, in
which Dimer Nitrogen Carboxy Esters are Probably
Involved in the Reaction Mechanisms as well as those of
Denitrification.

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Abstract

The reaction kinetics of nitrite oxidation have been examined using pulse tests in a single submerged biofilter that was previously used in a similar manner for the oxidation of ammonia. The fast recycle system, which acted as a batch reactor, ran on a Skinner and Walker medium. The starter bacteria were pure culture *Nitrosomonas europea* and *Nitrobacter europea*. Pulse testing as used in the process industries to examine dynamic processes allows the issues of short lived nitrite toxicity to be examined. The initial response to a large nitrite pulse is to reduce the nitrite concentrations to micro g/l levels within minutes. It was found necessary to add sulphuric acid to maintain the pH, which suggested the use of carboxy esters in nitrite oxidation. Once in the low micro g/l range the reactions follow Michaelis-Menten kinetics or possibly half order kinetics with very high chi-square fits. Hypothesised reaction mechanisms are presented based upon dimer carboxy ester reactions, with the substrates being oxidised via their respective carboxy esters.

Key words: Nitrification, Nitrite, Denitrification, Reaction kinetics, Mechanisms

1. Introduction

There are two main steps in nitrification. The first step, the oxidation of ammonia to nitrite, is done by archaea or bacteria using a peroxide enzyme followed by a hydrolysis reaction with another enzyme at a different location. The second nitrification step, the oxidation of nitrite to nitrate, involves entirely different archaea and bacteria with another hydrolysis enzyme. Furthermore denitrification can be considered an offshoot of the reactions and they too must have a place in the reaction scheme. It might be wondered why the reaction scheme follows this path.

The nitrite to nitrate hydrolysis reaction [1] stoichiometry is given by:

With respiration then forming water.

The overall reaction yields 73.2 KJ [2][3], which leads to very slow growth. The mean generation time was "uncommonly large at 10-15 hr" with 1 mole of organic material synthesised for 90 moles of substrate. Furthermore, Boon and Laudelout [4] indicated that *Nitrobacter winogradski* require low nitrite concentrations to grow. Nitrobacter are utilizing nitrite produced by the ammonia oxidisers, but they are also subjected to ammonia disturbances. In Painter's literature review it is indicated that "Aleem [5] reported that *Nitrobacter* is extremely sensitive to ammonia salts, especially at alkaline pH values, whereas the nitrite-oxidizing enzyme system derived from the organism is not".

The reaction kinetics of nitrite oxidation by *Nitrobacter winogradskyi* was extensively studied by Boon et al [4] using laboratory Warburg techniques. Based upon the relative rate of O₂ uptake they found that the reactions followed Michaelis-Menten type kinetics. From experiments at different pHs they suggested that inhibition by nitrous acid occurred. The relative rate of O₂ uptake

was also used to establish inhibition from nitrite and nitrate concentrations on the bacteria. Nitrite itself was shown to be inhibitory at the low $\mu\text{g} - \text{N}/\text{l}$ litre level. The inhibition of *Nitrobacter* by nitrate on the other hand was indicated to be negligible at the 50 mg/l $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ levels as occurring in the experiments here or in the recycle aquaculture system.

While Warburg experiments have yielded information regarding the reaction kinetics of nitrite oxidation, it is desirable to have methods that allow for the analysis of nitrification data from less controlled conditions. This could be for example in an aquaculture or an environmental setting, which are dynamic in nature. At near steady state conditions integrated kinetics plots can be used. A pulse and step testing approach, as used in the chemical industry, can also be used to investigate the reaction dynamics to understand potential toxicity issues.

2. Experimental

The experiments described here were done using *Nitrobacter europea* grown together with *Nitrosomonas europea* solely using ammonia as the substrate. The *Nitrobacter* thus grew in step with the ammonia oxidisers. The nitrate concentration rose as a result to levels similar to the recycle aquaculture system. The nitrite pulse testing experiments were carried out with the same high recycle experimental rig and in the same manner with the same methods [6] as for the ammonia pulse tests except with sodium nitrite. The nitrite pulse test experiments followed on from the ammonia ones with the same bacteria with the same oxygen levels. The ammonium sulphate dosing was switched off prior to the pulse tests. A pre-pulse test was conducted with the addition of sodium nitrite to yield a pulse equivalent to 1.2 mg/l nitrite-N. It was expected that it would take a long time for the bacteria to lower the nitrite concentration given that the typical nitrite concentrations were in the $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$ range rather than the mg/l range. The first sample was therefore taken after 15 minutes, but this sample and one 5 minutes later were already in the very low $\mu\text{g} - \text{N}/\text{l}$ range.

The main pulse tests were thus then conducted with the same pulse addition as the pre pulse test, but the sampling was started after 5 minutes. The nitrite experiments were monitored for 30 minutes thereafter. Furthermore, the pH of the system rose for more than 20 minutes before levelling out during the pre-pulse testing. Sulphuric acid was then chosen to maintain the pH during the main pulse experiments. Sulphate ions were already being added via ammonium sulphate in the medium.

3. Results

The pulse tests here indicate that *Nitrobacter europea* reacts very fast indeed to pulses in the nitrite concentration and reduces the nitrite concentrations to below 0.6 mg/1 nitrite-N after only 5 minutes. That is around half of the pulse reacts away in these first 5 minutes compared to 15 minutes for ammonia as shown in figure 1. This behaviour can be seen to optimise the process, but perhaps more importantly it also quickly lowers the nitrite levels and thus nitrite toxicity. There is no large difference in the reaction rate with regard to pH to the first sample as seen in figure 1, with a pH of 8.3 very slightly faster than that of 7.5 followed by 9.0. Unlike those for ammonia oxidation the integrated reaction plots, Michaelis-Menten kinetics is supported as shown in figure 2 over half order kinetics as given in Fig. 3. The first points are outside experimental error, but the other residuals show no significant trend. By taking the more diluted sample results at 9 min a more "consistent" trend can be achieved, but the overall chi fit is poorer.

The apparent Michaelis-Menten kinetics rate constants for nitrite oxidation are given in table 1. The nitrite reactions are some 30 % faster than that for ammonia oxidisers. This although the *Nitobacter* biofilm area is very likely a third of the total. It implies a very much faster reaction rate.

Figure 1: Nitrite Oxidation Rates

4. Discussion

According to the overall reaction stoichiometry, no acid should be required when conducting a short-lived pulse test. Protons and electrons are generated from the hydrolysis reaction, but they would be expected to be used in respiration. Indeed, no buffering of the system was required while growing the *Nitrobacter*. The quantities of sulphuric acid required indicated that significant amounts of acidic ions were removed in a short period of time. The amount of dosed acid required rose with increasing pH, particularly above 8.0. Bicarbonate ions form a significant constituent of freshwater and this strongly suggests that a carboxy phosphate ester is involved, as theorised with the oxidation of ammonia. The protons from nitrite hydrolysis can be used to maintain and control a low pH required for the substrate binding, but it is suspected that respiration would be favoured in generating ATP over proton pumping in normal circumstances.

Figure 2: Michaelis-Menten kinetics

The initial concentrations shown in Fig. 1 comparing ammonia and nitrite oxidation are the concentrations based upon instant ideal mixing. This is not strictly the case [7] and they were not used in the kinetic data analysis.

After around half of the substrate is consumed, the nitrite reaction at first inspection follows Michaelis-Menten kinetics as shown in figures 2. The kinetics would thus be in agreement with Boons findings [4] for *Nitrobacter winogradskyi*. The residuals do not reveal any control like behaviour, but a controlled response may occur before the start of the sampling. Unfortunately, the initial reactions seem to be so fast that without continuous measurements, and a second tracer to accounting for mixing effects, they could not be studied. The desire to take samples earlier conflicts with the goal to avoid mixing induced transients. The half order integrated plots are non-linear, but this does not rule out a reaction in which the concentration of say a carboxy ester is being optimised. Indeed the kinetic constants for half order kinetics are more consistent across the pH

Figure 3: Half Order kinetics

ranges.

4.1. Chemistry

The dimer dinitrogen tetroxide decomposes to nitrogen dioxide according to the equation below:

This suggests that NO_2 , a gas like NH_3 , could be the reactant in any biological equivalent reaction. In the Ostwald process ammonia is oxidised to nitrogen dioxide, via nitrogen oxide, using oxygen with a catalyst at high temperatures and pressures. Nitric acid is formed in the condensing water along with nitrogen oxide. The nitrogen oxide is recycled.

Nitrite Pulse Testing Data at Re 194

pH	R^2	$k_I a$	k_{II}
7.5	0.989	0.41	7.87
8.3	0.985	0.31	3.78
9.0	0.966	0.35	4.80

Table 1: Apparent Michaelis-Menten Kinetics Constants

Pulse Testing Data at Re 194

pH	R^2	$k_I a$
7.5	0.984	0.026
8.3	0.965	0.027
9.0	0.978	0.026

Table 2: Apparent Half Order Kinetic Constant

In organic chemistry nitrates can be formed from nitro groups via dinitro-addition followed by nitro-nitrosooxy-addition. The reaction is carried out with dinitrogen tetroxide and an olefin in a non-polar solvent. In the reaction, a nitrite ester intermediate that is "quite reactive" [8] (by organic chemistry standards) is formed. On oxidation with oxygen, the β - *nitroalkylnitrite* compound formed in the reaction is oxidized to the nitrate or the ketone. In the presence of water a nitro alcohol is formed. β - *nitroalkylperoxynitrates* can also be formed with excess oxygen. However, in the complete absence of oxygen β - *nitrosonitrate* is formed:

4.2. Nitrite Oxidation

The requirement to use an acid to hold the pH during the pulse tests, where under steady state conditions non was required, suggested a carboxy ester route could again be involved. In addition the nitroso nitrate of organic chemistry suggests a two carboxy ester reaction scheme with symmetry. One ester being reduced and the other oxidised.

The following mechanism for the oxidation of nitrite to nitrate is theorised. As it is a hydrolysis reaction the reverse reactions can also be facilitated. The first step in the oxidation of nitrite is proposed to aid the formation of the carboxy phosphate ester. The energy contained in the bonds of ATP is again assumed to be used to overcome thermodynamic barriers and the formation of nitrogen-based esters from the phosphate one. Aleem [9] found that nitrite oxidation proceeded significantly faster in the presence of iron ions than cupric ions. They suggested that iron is a component in nitrite oxidation. The experimental recycle rig contained no copper parts and the medium only traces of copper contained in the iron reagent. It can thus be suspected that the ester stabilising molecule contains iron rather than copper.

This is the same ester previously theorised to be involved in the oxidation of ammonia. This in turn poses an issue. It is theorised that it is the nitrite ester that is actually wanted. *Nitrobacter* needs to make and promote the nitrite ester while avoiding a reaction with ammonia to carbamate. High ammonia concentrations, as observed by Aleem [5], are then detrimental to nitrite oxidation. It might be speculated that his experiments with whole cells and a "nitrite oxidizing system" separated the two ester types which could be transported from different locations. If the ammonia oxidising bacteria are inhibited by toxic nitrite and nitrite oxidizing bacteria by ammonia, then a symbiotic relationship could occur. Nitrous acid is being shown as the substrate as in Boon's study [4], but it is felt that NO_2 is probably binding. "Nitrite oxidizing membranes possess a brownish colour which is typical for all nitrite oxidizers" [10]. This brownish colour is possibly the result of NO_2 formation.

Once the nitrogen esters are made there is no need of them in the reactions thereafter. To increase the reaction rate ATP could be used to make more of the nitrogen esters, but this is probably not such an issue if the ammonia oxida-

tion reactions producing the nitrite are slower. The nitrite hydrolysis reactions maybe fast, but the energy produced to enable growth is very low. As has already been mentioned[6], nitrous acid is not found naturally above pH 6.0. For an enzyme to catalyse the formation of nitrous acid in significant quantities the pH at the binding site has to be low. Unlike the oxidation of ammonia there are no protons as overall reaction products, but ones from the nitroso hydrolysis. There is thus the possibility of a pH binding control mechanism, but given the limits of the experimental method this cannot be confirmed.

4.3. The Theorised Mechanism and the Reaction Kinetics

As with the mechanisms for ammonia oxidation, those of nitrite oxidation need to match the observed kinetics. The theorised mechanisms involve multiple steps with the first forming carboxy nitrogen esters assumed to take place via the carboxy phosphate ester. The (hetro) dimer pair reaction involves the transfer of an oxygen atom leaving the nitroso to be hydrolysed. Finally the nitroso ester is hydrolysed.

Michaelis-Menten kinetics and observed half order kinetics both have valid chi-squared fits. The integrated Michaelis-Menten plots are as to be expected. Michaelis-Menten kinetics would be expected for the nitro ester equilibrium steps with the hydrolysis reaction being the slower step. The integrated half-order reaction plots on the other hand are not linear, which would suggest that the carboxy phosphate ester formation is not a limiting step. Thus once the carboxy nitrogen esters are made they are stable.

Michaelis-Menten kinetics and half order kinetics can be seen as simplifications of a more complex reaction mechanism with rate limiting steps. Binding and transport molecules could again be involved. The theorised mechanisms are based upon dimer pair ester reactions. If the nitrite concentration is very low then the formation of the dimer pair becomes more difficult and the number of "active" sites will be reduced. This would probably play a role in the observed kinetics.

Using simpler rate equations for biofilter designs which are valid over a wider

pH range has distinct advantages. The apparent rate constants are very similar at different pHs. Thus the bulk fluid pH is not influencing the supply of substrate to the reaction site much, as was also the case with ammonia oxidation. The theorised mechanisms do not require ATP once the nitrogen based esters are made, but as the overall reaction does not yield protons the production of ATP is constrained.

4.4. Denitrification

Denitrification can be seen as reactions that branch off from the nitrite ester reactions. The kinetics of denitrification and liquid film diffusion, at laboratory temperatures, in submerged biofilters has been examined by Christiansen [11] in conjunction with half order reaction kinetics. The superficial velocities used, which were indicated to be typical of those in waste water plants, were around a third of the lowest velocities used in the RAS nitrification study [12]. Recalculating the data at 5.6 m/h using a diffusion coefficient for nitrate of $1.9 \times 10^{-9} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$ [13] and the liquid film correlations of Dwivedi [14] yields a film transfer coefficients of $5.83 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}/\text{min}$. Fitting the flux equation for half-order kinetics with film diffusion [7] indicates that the reactions were in all probability not undergoing liquid film limitation (fitted $\bar{k}/h = 0.05$) and by extension biofilm diffusion limitation. Christiansen's figures 3 and 6c with the corresponding fits are given in Figure. 4. Liquid film diffusion can only be anticipated at bulk concentrations below 1 mg/l. Michaelis-Menten kinetics as indicated in 6c fits just as well as half-order kinetics. The real kinetics may indeed be Michaelis-Menten in nature, similar to the nitrite oxidation reactions, yielding apparent half-order fits at these higher concentrations. There is no reason to believe that the kinetics were zero order and diffusion limited below 10 mg/l. The experiments were repeated for different initial starting concentrations at different flowrates on different days. The theorised nitrogen carboxy ester mechanisms would have the differing curves arising from optimised ester concentrations rather than by a changing biofilm thickness as suggested by Christiansen.

Figure 4: Denitrification figures of Christiansen. Left: Half order plot (—) and fitted weak liquid film diffusion (---). Right: Half order (—) and fitted Michaelis-Menten kinetics (.....).

4.5. Oxygen

The presence of oxygen near the enzyme active site is assumed to inhibit the nitrite reaction through the formation of a nitro-nitrate. As the nitroso is not formed in the presence of oxygen, the protons and electrons are not obtained to provide energy. The energy loss from oxygen, and the drive for overall energy efficiency, is speculated to result in the two steps in nitrification done by two sets of bacteria. It follows that nitrite bacteria require that respiration is remote from the hydrolysis reaction. Ammonia oxidation is proceeding using a peroxide formed from oxygen, and benefits from higher oxygen levels. Nitrite and other nitrogen ester reactions will be more efficient if they occur in lower oxygen environments, that is following ammonia oxidation. On the other hand, the ammonia oxidisers are inhibited by nitrite. There would thus be some overall

energy recovery optimum in which separation of the reactions involving two sets of bacteria is beneficial to both.

4.6. Ultraviolet Light

Both *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrobacter* are known to be inhibited by visible blue and ultraviolet light [15][16][17]. The oxygenated copper catalytic cycle based on tyrosinase was chosen by Shears and Wood [18] because of its sensitivity to ultraviolet light. This could explain the sensitivity of ammonium mono-oxygenase to ultraviolet light, but it does not explain that of *Nitrobacter*. This "unexplained feature of nitrite oxidation" [19] can be answered by the proposed mechanisms. It is proposed that light interferes with the nitro-nitroso groups in nitrification.

Nitro and nitroso groups as given in the proposed mechanisms undergo many photochemical reactions. Based on the reactions of nitromethane, the carbon-nitrogen-oxygen bonds are known to break, leading to other re-arrangements. Morrison gives a table of reactions in "The chemistry of the nitro and nitroso groups (part 1)" [20]. The theorised mechanisms suggest that the reactions of both ammonia oxidation, at least in bacteria, and nitrite oxidation will be influenced by UV light.

4.7. Nitrous-Oxide and Dinitrogen

Under low oxygen tension (anoxic/anaerobic) conditions, denitrification occurs in nitrifiers. Nitrite reductase has been found in *Nitrosomonas europea* [21][22] and it is assumed to be responsible for the observed production of nitrous oxide. This is in agreement with Poth and Focht's [23] ^{15}N isotope studies, which indicated that *Nitrosomonas europea* makes nitrous oxide via two unstable intermediates involving nitrite. The authors also made pertinent comments on the need to determine the influence of diffusion at very low concentrations in laboratory methods. Miller [21] found that a copper site in nitrite reductase had a "high affinity" for O_2 , to such an extent that accurate measurement of its affinity was precluded. Therefore, copper complexes are probably involved in

the formation of nitrous oxides and dinitrogen, although iron complexes could also play a transportation role. Carboxy-sulphur esters and sulphur oxides could bind to iron.

If denitrification reactions follow the theme of the carboxy ester mechanism, then the reactions are expected to be carboxy bound versions of those found in nitrous acid chemistry and organic chemistry [8]. In dilute solutions kinetic reaction control can dominate over thermodynamic reaction control. Two carboxy nitro esters could yield carboxy bound nitrogen trioxide and water via nitrogen tetraoxide. With the ammonia carboxy ester, nitrogen trioxide could be transformed into nitrous-oxide and nitrite. Nitrous-oxide could also be made via the nitroso carboxy ester and hydroxamic acid.

The overall carboxy ester for nitrous-oxide reaction is:

The need to add sulphuric acid in the first 5 minutes (before the first sample) to maintain the pH in the nitrite pulse tests, where no ammonia was added, could have been due to increased carboxy ester formation, but possibly the result of the nitrite bacteria making nitrous-oxide to lower the toxicity.

Other bacteria, which contain nitrate reductase can convert nitrates, presumably via nitrites, to atmospheric nitrogen. As was indicated by Wood [19], ammonia-oxidizing bacteria "would do much better to oxidize ammonia to nitrogen gas". The reaction of ammonia with nitrous acid has a Gibbs free energy of negative 360 kJ/mol. This reaction is well-known in chemistry. It may be

thought that ammonia gas could react with nitrous acid to form nitrogen gas, but the high pH required for ammonia gas formation contrasts with the low pH required for the nitrite reactions. If the ammonia carboxy ester is used instead of the ammonia gas itself, and subsequently an acid is formed, then the local low pH requirements could be met. Mechanisms involving carboxy esters, such as those for nitrous oxide, can thus be considered. The single oxygen atom in nitrous-oxide could be removed with either protons or molecules using an oxygen atom. The question of why ammonia is not converted directly to dinitrogen does not arise because it is the carboxy esters of the "substrates" that are being oxidized and reduced, not the substrates themselves. Furthermore kinetic reaction control maybe dominating. In the event that ammonia is absent in sufficient quantities, protons will be required from other sources.

4.8. Nitrite Diffusion

Nitrobacter growing in close proximity to the *Nitrosomonas* would be experiencing the biofilm surface concentrations directly from the ammonia oxidisers rather than bulk concentrations. The pulse test experiments here have the nitrite diffusing from the bulk with higher concentrations reducing the effect of liquid film diffusion on the rate. Once the diffusion coefficient for nitrite oxidation can be established the reaction kinetics of ammonia to nitrate oxidation could in theory be calculated. It is suspected that this approach is too simplistic. The two sets of bacteria probably are controlling and optimising the reactions

while striving to stay within toxicity limits. Given the speed at which nitrite can be oxidised if necessary, it would seem that nitrite toxicity issues are not to be expected in normal biofilter operations. On the other hand, man induced step changes to the ammonia load from rapid stock increases in an aquaculture system for example can. *Nitrobacter* grow much more slowly than *Nitrosomonas* on account of the less energy derived from their reactions.

4.9. Anammox Process

In 1995 Mulder [24], a decade after anaerobic ammonia oxidation was established in nitrifiers, presented evidence for anaerobic ammonium oxidation (Anammox) reactions at very high ammonia concentrations in a waste water setting. The metabolic pathway of the bacterial culture was shortly afterwards investigated by van de Graaf [25] using ^{15}N labelled ammonia, nitrite, nitrate and hydroxylamine. Not only was hydroxylamine used as a feed, but hydrazine too. They envisaged dinitrogen to be made from hydroxylamine, obtained from nitrite, and ammonia via hydrazine. Schalk [26] found a high conversion of hydrazine and nitrite, but no hydroxylamine, nitrous oxide or nitrate was detected. The bacteria used in the Anammox process have been found to come from the phylum Planctomycetota. Hooper [27] proposed that NO rather than hydroxylamine reacts with ammonia to yield hydrazine. The carboxy ester nitrogen mechanisms given here provide several alternative possible mechanisms without the production of free hydrazine, which is even more toxic than hydroxylamine. Woulter [28] measured trace amounts of hydrazine from very large hydroxylamine pulse experiments. Experiments into the Anammox process have been conducted at very high ammonia concentrations, where the doubling time is between 7 to 22 days [29], far from those in natural watercourses where liquid film diffusion of ammonia can also play a role.

5. Conclusion

Surprisingly sulphuric acid was needed to maintain the pH during the pulse tests. The amounts increased with the experimental pH. This behaviour sug-

gests that a carboxy ester mechanism is involved in nitrite oxidation. After a pulse input, similar in magnitude to those conducted with ammonia, nitrite to nitrate oxidation occurs considerably faster than that of ammonia to nitrite. Indeed so fast that continuous measurements, with an additional tracer, would be required to separate mixing transients and the reaction kinetics at reaction times under 5 minutes. Examining the reaction kinetics for time intervals greater than 5 minutes reveals that Michaelis-Menten kinetics and half order kinetics give excellent chi probabilities. The integrated plots suggest that of the two, Michaelis-Menten kinetics is followed. Theorised nitrification mechanisms are given with the substrate reactions occurring via carboxy ester pairs rather than the nitrite substrate directly. One ester is oxidised and the other reduced. Importantly the mechanisms allow for the control and optimisation of the reactions as demanded by evolution. The theorised reactions are compatible with experimental observations by other authors and indicate as to why nitrification proceeds in two steps by two sets of bacteria. It is suggested that ammonia and nitrite oxidisers have a symbiotic relationship that results in very good handling of disturbances. As nitrite oxidisers grow slower than ammonia oxidisers nitrite peaks can nevertheless occur from large step changes in ammonia levels.

Nomenclature

Symbols

a	Specific surface area	m^2/m^3
C	Concentration of Total Nitrite Nitrogen	mg/l
d_p	Equivalent particle diameter	m
$k_{I...III}$	apparent rate equation constants (units depend upon equation)	
R^2	Correlation Coefficient	
t	Time after First Sample	min

u Superficial velocity m/s

Other Symbols

μ Dynamic Viscosity $kg/m/s$

ρ Particle density kg/m^3

Dimensionless Numbers

$Re = \rho u d_p / \mu$ Reynolds number

Subscripts

fit Fitted Time

i Initial Concentration

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